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Influence of Counsellors' Gender On Students' choice of Counselor in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the Influence of Counsellors' Gender On Students' choice of Counselor in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The study was guided by two purpose of study, two research questions and two hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The research design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised of 80 students from senior secondary school one to three. Purposive sampling technique was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 10 item questionnaire structured on a four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in guidance and counselling and another in Measurement and Evaluation. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and it yielded a coefficient value of 0.81. Mean and standard deviation and t-test statistics was used to test the two hypotheses formulated for the study. The results indicated that male students opined that they are more comfortable with a male counselor as they are at liberty to do the following during a counselling section with a male counselor; discuss personal issues, life issues, career issues, life problems and are usually reserved while interacting with a female counsellor and gender influences female students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis in the following ways; it increases their interest, enhances openness, guarantees some level of safety and creates the right attitude while they are interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section. Based on the findings, conclusions were made. The study recommended among other things that The gender of counselors should be properly balanced to enable male and female students to make choice in the gender of counselors that they are comfortable with to enable them make inform in the gender of counselors in a school. That is, schools should consider posting both gender of counsellors to secondary schools so that students can be at liberty to a counselor of choice based on their gender.

Keywords: Counselling, counsellor, gender, guidance.

INTRODUCTION

Counselling is a very important aspect of students' life as it enables them to get assistance and directions on their areas of worries and concerns by interacting with professional counselors who are knowledgeable on the areas that students have concerns as it will hem to get right direction that they need in the regard.

There are significant roles that counselors play in the molding the lives of individuals especially the younger ones like students in various secondary schools irrespective of their gender (Bakare,2021). Counselors provide professional guidance to students at various level of education especially secondary schools because the students at this level of education are usually at a very sensitive stage of their life where major decisions are taken (Bakare,2021). However, it is also important to note that the gender of a counselor plays significant role in the students' choice of that counselor as some students are more comfortable with the gender of a particular counsellor while some of the student are usually not comfortable with the gender of a particular counsellor when it comes to counselling (Watkins, 2023).

There are about one hundred and fifteen guidance counsellor personnel engaged in rendering services in guidance and counselling in Rivers State (Rivers State ministry of education, 2018). About one hundred and one of them received professional training up to bachelor degree, few others, less than one hundred of them got higher degrees and diploma certificate in guidance and counselling, (Rivers State ministry of education, 2018). The rest of them are either career masters or those chosen by individual schools to take charge of guidance services with the students and significant others. The notion of having career masters in schools is in line with the Federal Government directive in the National Policy on Education (2004) that schools that have no trained counsellors should select some of their teachers and train internally for the purpose of helping the maladjusted behaviors of the secondary school students (Oyinloye, 2019 and Gale,2015) opined that lack of trust, confidence as well as the slow pace of counselling in our schools is alarming. Some of the reasons popularly advanced for the failure of counselling services in schools ranges from the shortage of guidance counsellors, scarcity of funds to the attitudes of students and counsellor's sex. These have generated some heated arguments over the years unresolved.

Several studies have shown students' choice of counsellors by gender. While some of the research findings indicated that male students prefer male counsellors during counselling, others indicated that male clients prefer female counsellors. In the same way, evidence from some other studies revealed that female students generally like female counsellors to attend to them during counselling. Okoroafor (2023) and Watkins (2023) found in their studies that the sex of the counsellor affect students' lack of interest and attitude variation towards guidance and counselling services in schools. Bakare (2021) found that female students like choosing male counsellors because of the influence of opposite sex on interaction. This contradicts Dickson (2018) who earlier found that female students prefer female counsellors during counselling sessions. Okon (2021) have also contended that male students would always like to discuss career, personal- social and life problems with male counsellors because of their wealth of experience and cordial approach. The contention of Ikeotuonye and Okon (2020) above seemed controversial because guidance and counselling is usually seen as a woman's job (Ifelunni, 2020). As the controversy rages on, the gap (which is placed on sex in counselling) becomes necessary to be filled hence Robert (2021) conducted a study on female students response to counselor's gender, it was fund that female students preferred male counsellors during counselling relationship.

Statement of the problem

Counselling is a very important aspect of students' life as it enables them to get assistance and directions on their areas of worries and concerns by interacting with professional counselors who are knowledgeable on the areas that students have concerns as it will enable them to get the right direction that they need in this regard. Since the inception of guidance and counselling services by Federal Government in the National Policy on Education (2004), it has suffered serious disadvantages. Most of the secondary schools do not have trained counsellors and some that have it do not have a balance in terms of gender while the few with guidance counsellors have not lived up to expectations in terms of the provision of counselling services. The concern is whether the counsellor's gender could be responsible for the secondary school students' attitude towards counselling. And if the sex of the counsellor can affect the student's attitude negatively, which of the sexes will be preferred by the male students and females students. This study is to ascertain the most preferred gender of counsellor by students. It is on this ground that this study sought to determine the Influence of Counsellors' Gender On Students' choice of Counselor in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of Counsellors' Gender On Students' choice of Counselor in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the influence of gender on male students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?
2. Determine the influence of gender on female students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. To what extent does gender influence male students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.
2. To what extent does gender influence female students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of female students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

METHOD

The study examined Influence of Counsellors' Gender On Students' choice of Counselor in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. Two research objectives with two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study. Population of the study consisted of 80 students. The Instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire validated by 3 experts, two from Guidance and counselling and one from measurement and evaluation. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze research questions while t-test was used to analyze the research hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does gender influence male students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Gender Influence Male Students' Choice of Counselors In Public Secondary Schools In Port-Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	OBALGA (28)			PHALGA (34)		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
1.	Am usually comfortable discussing career matters with a male counsellor.	3.76	0.75	HE	3.59	0.72	HE
2.	I discuss personal life matters with a male counsellor	3.69	0.74	HE	3.55	0.71	HE
3.	I discuss social life matters with a male counsellor	3.78	0.74	HE	3.71	0.74	HE
4.	I discuss life problems with a male counsellor	3.72	0.74	HE	3.54	0.71	HE
5.	Am usually reserved discussing personal matters with a female counsellor.	3.76	0.75	HE	3.70	0.74	HE
	Total Mean/SD	18.71	3.72		18.09	3.62	
	Grand Mean/SD	3.74	0.74		3.62	0.72	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 1 shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent. This, indicates that male students opined that they can do the following during a counselling section with a male counselor; discuss

personal issues, life issues, career issues, life problems and are usually reserved while interacting with a female counsellor.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does gender influence female students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Gender Influence Female Students' Choice of Counselors in Public Secondary Schools In Port-Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	OBALGA (28)			PHALGA (34)		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
6.	Interacting with a female counsellor increases my interest during a counselling section.	3.60	0.72	HE	3.55	0.71	HE
7.	Interacting with a female counsellor enhances my openness during a counselling section.	3.57	0.71	HE	3.53	0.71	HE
8.	I feel safe while interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section.	3.76	0.75	HE	3.56	0.71	HE
9.	Am at liberty to talk freely while interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section.	3.66	0.73	HE	3.57	0.71	HE
10.	I usually have the right attitude while interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section.	3.61	0.72	HE	3.53	0.71	HE
Total Mean/SD		18.20	3.63		17.74	3.55	
Grand Mean/SD		3.64	0.73		3.55	0.71	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 2 shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent. This, indicates that gender influence female students' choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis in the following ways; it increases their interest, enhances openness, guarantees some level of safety and creates the right attitude while they are interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section.

Hypotheses Test

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

Table 3: T-test of Difference between the Mean Ratings of Male Students in Public Secondary Schools in PHALGA and OBALGA On The Extent Gender Influences Choice Of Counselors.

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign	Decision
OBALGA	28	3.74	0.74	78	0.6	2.000	0.05	Accepted
PHALGA	34	3.62	0.72					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 3 shows that the t-calculated is less than the t-critical ($t\text{-cal} < t\text{-crit}$). Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of female students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

Table 4: T-test of Difference between the Mean Ratings of Female Students In Public Secondary Schools in PHALGA and OBALGA On The Extent Gender Influences Choice Of Counselors.

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign	Decision
OBALGA	28	3.64	0.73	78	0.53	2.000	0.05	Accepted
PHALGA	34	3.55	0.71					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From the analysis in table 4 shows that the t-calculated is less than the t-critical ($t\text{-cal} < t\text{-crit}$). Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of female students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The findings in table one shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent. This, indicates that male students opined that they can do the following during a counselling section with a male counselor; discuss personal issues, life issues, career issues, life problems and are usually reserved while interacting with a female counsellor and there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

This finding is agreement with the view of Okon (2021) who opined that; that male students would always like to discuss career, personal– social and life problems with male counsellors because of their wealth of experience and cordial approach.

The findings in table two shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent. This, indicates that gender influence female students’ choice of counselors in public secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis in the following ways; it increases their interest, enhances openness, guarantees some level of safety and creates the right attitude while they are interacting with a female counsellor during a counselling section and there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of female students in public secondary schools in PHALGA and OBALGA on the extent gender influences choice of counselors.

This finding is agreement with the view of Dickson (2018) who opined that; female students prefer female counsellors during counselling sessions. In agreement with the view of Dickson, Okoroafor (2023) and Watkins (2023) found in their studies that the sex of the counsellor affect students’ lack of interest and attitude variation towards guidance and counselling services in schools.

CONCLUSION

The gender of counsellors have been observed to have a strong influence on the operations of guidance and counselling in secondary schools. The male students appear to be free with the male counselors in cases about educational, career, vocational, informational and other dimensions of counselling order than personal-social matters while the female students have more interest,open, feel safe, and have the right attitude when they are interacting with female counselors during counselling sessions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1.The gender of counselors should be properly balanced to enable male and female students to make choice in the gender of counselors that they are comfortable with to enable them make inform in the gender of counselors in a school. That is, schools should consider posting both gender of counsellors to secondary schools so that students can be at liberty to a counselor of choice based on their gender.

2. Relevant authorities should place emphasis on the nature of students in terms of gender as it influences their choice of counselors so that the essence of introducing counselling can be well achieved.

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